

Avicenna Alliance

Plain language *in silico* medicine glossary

Introductory note

As the field of in silico medicine is rapidly advancing, new terms and concepts are frequently introduced, often before a consensus on definitions may have been reached. To help promote the understanding of the often specialised technical vocabulary and make the field of in silico medicine accessible to everybody, we have created this plain language glossary.

Disclaimer: *We recognise that the language in this area is continually evolving and that alternative definitions may exist. We welcome [feedback and suggestions](#), as this glossary is intended to be a dynamic resource that grows and adapts over time. In instances where there may be a discrepancy between this glossary and the more detailed [technical glossary](#), the latter shall be considered to provide the more technically accurate definition. Our goal is to enhance understanding and facilitate informed discussions about in silico medicine, making it more approachable for everyone.*

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Glossary terms

Carers or caregivers

Carers or caregivers are “persons supporting individual patients, such as family members as well as paid or volunteer helpers with activities of daily living” (from [Hunter et al.](#)).

Computational modelling

Computational modelling is a way of using computers to simulate and study how complex systems behave and interact. By entering data and using mathematical rules, these simulations help researchers understand patterns, predict future outcomes, and solve challenges in areas such as health, engineering, or the environment, without needing to conduct real-world experiments.

Computational modelling & simulation (CM&S) in healthcare

Computational modelling and simulation (CM&S) is a method that uses computer programming, advanced calculations, and powerful computers to create and run simulations based on fundamental scientific rules. This approach helps researchers understand how things might behave in the real world by virtually testing them on computers. CM&S is particularly promising in medicine, where it can improve, fine-tune, or even replace aspects of physical experiments and clinical studies. This means we can explore new treatments, solve complex problems, or predict future events more efficiently, safer, and with fewer physical resources.

Digital evidence (i.e., *in silico* evidence)

Digital evidence is the results from computer simulations used in the approval process for new medical treatments or technologies. It comes from virtual experiments and tests, provided in a set format, to help decide if these new developments are safe and effective.

Digital twin

A digital twin is a virtual copy of something real – be it something physical, a process, or an entire system. This virtual copy is designed to learn and improve over time, getting information from different places, sometimes immediately as things happen (real-time events/inputs). It serves as a link between the real and the digital worlds, making it possible to run tests or analyses in the computer, to predict potential issues before they happen, or help make plans for the future. A digital twin is a tool that helps us understand and interact with the real world in a safer, more efficient way by experimenting and planning in the digital space.

Engaged research

Engaged research “describes a wide range of rigorous research approaches and methodologies that share a common interest in collaborative engagement with the community. It aims to improve, understand, or investigate an issue of public interest or concern, including societal challenges. Engaged research is advanced with community partners rather than for or about them. ‘Community’ refers to a range of public research stakeholders, including public or professional service and product users, policy makers, civil and civic society organisations (CSOs) and actors” (from [Campus Engage](#)).

Genome-scale metabolic reconstruction

A genome-scale metabolic reconstruction is a mathematical representation of an organism's metabolism, i.e., of the chemical reactions occurring in the organism. Genome-scale metabolic reconstructions enable the computational modelling of human metabolism. While a reconstruction is a generic description of an organism (e.g., human), it can be tailored to a specific individual using person-specific biomedical data, to create a personalised metabolic model.

In silico

In silico, literally 'in silicon' is a term used to describe experiments or processes done on a computer (as computer chips are made from silicon). It is a way of saying 'in the computer' or 'through computer simulation'. This is similar to how '*in vitro*' means experiments done in a lab dish, '*ex vivo*' refers to studies outside a living organism but using its parts, and '*in vivo*' means studies done inside the living organism. *In silico* allows researchers to simulate and study complex scenarios without physical experiments, using computer technology to investigate and predict how things might work in real life.

***In silico* trials (IST)**

In silico trials are a type of computer-simulated tests used for evaluating new treatments, like drugs or medical devices. These tests use computer models and simulations to imitate traditional laboratory tests (*in vitro*, *ex vivo*) and experiments conducted on animals or humans (*in vivo*). The goal is to produce digital evidence that can be used in the process of getting regulatory approval. These trials must follow specific, standardised conditions. They are also known as *in silico* experiments, emphasising their role in testing treatments through simulations rather than physical experiments.

***In silico* clinical trial (ISCT)**

An *in silico* clinical trial is a computer-simulated test to evaluate new medicines or medical devices. It uses computer models and simulations to replicate the human testing that is typically required for regulatory approval. These simulations are done under strict, predefined conditions with models that have been thoroughly checked and confirmed for accuracy. The process involves creating virtual patients or groups of virtual patients to see how they might respond to a treatment. This method helps predict the effectiveness and safety of medical interventions without initial real-world testing on people.

***In silico* evaluation**

In silico evaluation is a method of testing and analysing new products like medicines or materials using computer simulations instead of physical experiments. This type of evaluation uses computer models to predict how a substance will act in a biological system or how a material will perform under different environmental conditions. It is a cost-effective and time-efficient way to refine and improve products without the risks, expenses, and delays of traditional laboratory or field tests.

***In silico* method (ISM)**

In silico method refers to using computer-based tools to conduct experiments, evaluations, or analyses. These methods involve creating and using computer models to simulate real-life processes or experiments. There are three main types of *in silico* methods:

1. ***In silico* test (or experiment or study):** This is like doing a laboratory test (*in vitro*) or an experiment using parts of organisms (*ex vivo*) but in a computer setting. It allows researchers to investigate how something might work in a controlled environment without physical testing.

2. ***In silico* medicine:** This involves using computer simulations, including tailored to individual patients, to help in all stages of medical care — from prevention and diagnosis to predicting outcomes and planning treatments.
3. ***In silico* trial:** This is the use of computer simulations to test new medical treatments or devices, aiming to provide the necessary evidence for regulatory approval.

Involved research

Involved research “refers to co-created and co-produced research with a focus on collaboration” (from [Campus Engage](#)).

Metabolism

Metabolism is the set of chemical reactions occurring in living organisms. These reactions allow organisms to grow, reproduce, maintain their structures, and respond to their environments. Metabolism includes how our bodies convert the food we eat into the energy we need to function and the building blocks needed for growth and repair.

Microbiome

The microbiome refers to the collection of all the tiny organisms, like bacteria, fungi, and viruses, that live in a particular environment, such as the human body or soil. In humans, these organisms live inside (e.g., our gut) and on us (e.g., our skin). They play important roles in our health, e.g., in metabolism.

Model

A model is a simplified version of something from the real world that helps us understand or study it better. Think of it as a miniature or a basic outline that captures the essential parts of a system—like a car, the weather, or a business process. By creating models, we can experiment with changes, make predictions, and plan improvements without affecting the real thing. This makes it faster, safer, and cheaper to explore different scenarios and find solutions to challenges.

Modelling

Modelling is the process of using specific tools to represent and analyse something in the real world, usually complex systems. This helps us understand and predict how a system behaves, e.g., by simulating it on a computer.

Patient advocates

Patient advocates are “persons who have the insight and experience in supporting a larger population of patients living with a specific disease” (from [Hunter et al.](#)). They may or may not be affiliated with an organisation, and may or not be patients themselves.

Patient contributor

A patient contributor is an “individual with personal experience of living with a disease. They may or may not have technical knowledge in research, development, or regulatory processes, but their main role is to contribute with their subjective disease and treatment experience” (from [Hunter et al.](#)).

Patient experts

Patient experts are *“in addition to disease-specific expertise, persons who have the technical knowledge in R&D, regulatory, or public affairs through training or experience, e.g., EUPATI Fellows who have been trained by EUPATI on the full spectrum of medicines R&D”* (from [Hunter et al.](#)).

Patient organisation representatives

Patient organisation representatives are *“persons who are mandated to represent and express the collective views of a patient organisation on a specific issue or disease area”* (from [Hunter et al.](#)).

Research participation

Research participation refers to the act of individuals joining and taking part in a study or experiment. It involves people volunteering to donate data or undergo certain procedures that contribute to research objectives.

Risk analysis

Risk analysis is the process of using a model to understand the impact of different choices and to see what might happen as a result. It helps us assess potential outcomes, and make informed decisions by combining our understanding of the system with what could occur if we choose one action over another.

Science communication and outreach

“Science communication and outreach broadly describes the practice of communicating science-related topics to wider and non-expert audiences. This might include young people, politicians, journalists, education professionals and so on” (from [Palestine Academy for Science & Technology](#)). Science outreach implies a primarily one-way mode of communication.

System

A system is a set of things – like organs in a body or parts in a machine — that work together in a specific way to achieve a certain goal. These things interact or depend on each other under certain conditions. When we study or talk about a system, we may focus only on certain parts and how they contribute how the system behaves.

Uncertainty

Uncertainty refers to the unknowns and potential errors in any part of a modelling, computing, or experimenting process. Uncertainty may be exist because of random factors or because we do not have complete or accurate information.

Validation

Validation is the process of checking that a model accurately reflects the real-world situation it is supposed to represent. Validation ensures that the model can be trusted for its intended purpose.

Variables

Variables are quantities in a model that can change based on other factors or data within the simulation. Their values are not fixed and may vary as the simulation progresses.

Virtual patient

A virtual patient is a computer simulation that represents unique characteristics of an individual person, such as their anatomy, health condition, or lifestyle. This simulation may interact with a medical intervention to predict outcomes, rather than measuring them through physical tests. Virtual patients can help make decisions about diagnoses or treatments in a specific situation.

Workflow

A workflow in scientific settings refers to the series of steps involved in carrying out research or interventions. Common stages include data collection, analysis, visualisation, interpretation, and sharing. Workflows can be mapped out visually with diagrams or described using algorithms.